

MECHANISMS OF STRENGTHENING AND HEALTH OF THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL ENVIRONMENT IN FAMILIES THROUGH PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article examines and illuminates the conditions, mechanisms, and diagnosis models for establishing positive traditions of family, educational institution and community cooperation, and for improving the spiritual and moral environment in families.*

Keywords: *Physical education, physical culture, family, family upbringing, family relations, valeological education, physical and mental activity.*

МЕХАНИЗМЫ УКРЕПЛЕНИЯ И ЗДОРОВЬЯ ДУХОВНО-МОРАЛЬНОЙ СРЕДЫ В СЕМЬЕ С ПОМОЩЬЮ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются и освещаются условия, механизмы и модели диагностики формирования позитивных традиций семейно-образовательного и общественного сотрудничества, оздоровления духовно-нравственной среды в семьях.*

Ключевые слова: *физическое воспитание, физическая культура, семья, семейное воспитание, семейные отношения, валеологическое воспитание, физическая и умственная деятельность.*

INTRODUCTION

The thinkers of the East recognized that it is possible to cultivate such qualities as generosity, honesty, patriotism, respect for the opponent, and respect for nature, precisely under the influence of physically stimulating national games.

In the West, physical education and physical training were considered as an important part of family education and the pedagogical process at school in the Middle Ages.

According to the research, when the spiritual and moral environment in families is strengthened through physical education, the multifaceted and complex nature of this process is shown.

METHODOLOGY

When the spiritual and moral environment in families is strengthened through physical education, it is a mechanism that represents the process, depending on its function, it organizes the process and transmits the action; executor (participant in the educational process, executor); manager, supervisor and adjuster (teacher, parents, psychologist, school administration, social institutions, state); the one who ensures that the process goes correctly (teacher, parents, social institutions), sorter (educational institution, management, teacher), who carries out promotional activities (promotional events, challenges, patterns); It is embodied in components such as productivity monitors (community organizations, school administration, neighborhood activists, teachers, parents).

Propaganda carried out in a school institution	Propaganda carried out in the family
To give clear recommendations to the student on the correct planning of the	Regular exercise in the morning

agenda.	
Meaning they have an understanding of the release of happy hormones while running	Organization of physical and mental activity in harmony
Cultivating voluntary qualities in regular participation in mass sports	Adequate and quality sleep conditions, compliance with nutrition rules
Learning to accept victory and defeat easily	Being able to follow moral standards in different situations
Development of spiritual and moral qualities	Spiritual (the inner world closely connected with the mind and psyche of family members: knowledge, purity of heart, generosity, sincerity, benevolence, faith, honesty, faith, piety, purity, compassion) and moral (doing good, forgiveness, patience) , honesty, sweetness, respect for parents, elders, honor, loyalty) and be able to show them as an example

Table 1. Promotional forms aimed at organizing physical education in educational organizations and families.

The positive change of the spiritual and moral environment in families through physical education, its direct impact on the subject being educated, its dependence on the team of teachers who manage the pedagogical process, and its relation to the behavior evaluated by the responsibility of parents. Research based on the provision of the Special Experience Program in 2018-2022 it became clear during

The mechanism of strengthening the spiritual and moral environment in families through physical education requires the use of educational methods and tools that serve to solve issues related to the spiritual and educational sphere and guide young people to a healthy lifestyle (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Mechanisms of strengthening and health of spiritual and moral environment in families

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The parameters of the mechanism intended for education are enriched based on the resources related to the control mechanism (tools with an educational effect - physical training exercises, spiritual and moral activities, books, films, challenges, etc.). Pedagogical management actions are formed by the system of spiritual education. A system subject to external influence - control (control actions) is called a controlled system (control object). Together, these two systems are considered as an independent health system, taking into account their interaction.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

From our analyzes on the stabilization of a healthy lifestyle in the family, it was found that the achievement of high efficiency in the spheres of spiritual-educational and physical maturity of young people is under the positive influence of education. It became clear that the spiritual and moral environment in the family is stabilized with the help of examples, persuasion, radiating, and pedagogical methods of setting an example, that is, the cases where parents themselves regularly engage in physical education, train their children physically, and act as a personal example, extrapolate (predictive) the effect of physical education in the case of a pedagogical phenomenon methods) made it possible to use.

The article examines and illuminates the conditions, mechanisms, and diagnosis models for establishing positive traditions of family, educational institution and community cooperation, and for improving the spiritual and moral environment in families.

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